

PHILOLOGICAL SCIENCES

COGNITIVE FEATURES OF BORROWINGS IN ENGLISH-LANGUAGE TEXTS

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Abstract

The cognitive characteristics of borrowings in English-language texts is an important topic from the point of view of language development and analysis of linguistics. This article examines the cognitive effects of borrowed words from different languages into English. Borrowings lead to changes in the semantic, phonological and syntactic structures of the language. Within the framework of the theory of cognitive linguistics, how the borrowed words affect the brain processes of assimilation and memorization and the influence of cross-cultural relations on language are studied. Borrowings also affect the social and communicative aspects of language, as language users acquire new language elements in different social and cultural contexts.

Borrowings are words that are transferred from one language to another and adapted to the laws of that language. Within the framework of cognitive linguistics, the question of how borrowings are received and assimilated in the human brain is important. Cognitive linguistics emphasizes that language is not only a communication tool, but also a system that reflects how people think and understand the world. This approach, while analyzing the cognitive aspects of language, allows us to understand the meaning structure of language and how language works in our brains.

Keywords: borrowings, cognitive, English language, semantics, phonology, syntax.

Introduction

Language occupies an important place in people's lives as a means of culture, thought and communication. Each language, over time, establishes contacts with other languages, and as a result, various language elements, especially words, pass from one language to another, increasing the richness of that language. One of these linguistic phenomena is borrowings. Modern English language is the product of long-term historical development. Its sound composition, grammatical structure and lexicon have undergone indirect changes for various reasons - wars, conquests, travels, trade, etc. During its development, English has borrowed words from more than 50 languages over 1500 years, as its speakers have established various contacts with other language speakers in Europe and other continents. This fact is the reason why there are so many foreign language elements in the lexical composition of modern English.

Borrowings usually enter the language as a result of language mixing and cultural-historical, socio-economic and other relations between peoples. These processes stem from the interaction of different cultures and languages, and create a rich foreign vocabulary in the English language.

During its historical development, the English language has mixed with the Scandinavian languages, as well as with the Norman dialect of French. In addition, throughout its history, English has had more or less contact with Latin, French, Spanish, Russian, German and other languages, so linguistic connections have arisen between these languages. As a result of the mixing of languages and cultural and economic relations between peoples, the interaction between languages is not equal, and the results of the influence of one language on another are different. The number and nature

of borrowed words mainly depend on the specific historical circumstances in which one language influenced another.

Words borrowed from Scandinavian into English are fewer than words borrowed from French as a result of contact between these languages, and words borrowed from French make up about 60% of the English lexicon. The stability of these words depends on several factors. The most important reason is that the borrowed word successfully identifies a sub-meaning or manifestation of a previously existing notion. The reinforcement of borrowed words in English occurs through their adaptation to phonetic and morphological rules. The language tends to accept these words in their original form rather than adapting them to the forms of existing English notions.

At the same time, it should be noted that foreign words borrowed from the literary lexicon retain their original form for a certain period of time. For example, accents, graphic appearance and pronunciation remain unchanged. In very rare cases, the preservation of plural forms is observed. As a result, borrowed words change their original meanings, which is a natural process. Also, borrowed words can acquire new meanings. Borrowed words in English have arisen mainly as a result of historical and cultural exchanges. Although the English language originally arose from the Old Germanic languages, throughout history it has adopted thousands of borrowings from French, Latin, Greek and other languages.

1. **French Borrowings:** As a result of the Norman Conquest in 1066, French had a strong influence on English. During this period, numerous borrowings from French appeared in English. For example, words such as "**court**", "**parliament**", and "**government**" have been borrowed from French.

2. **Latin and Greek Borrowings:** Latin and Greek words, which are most commonly used in scientific and religious texts, represent classical knowledge and scientific notions in English. For example, words such as “**philosophy**”, “**science**”, and “**universe**” have been borrowed from Latin and Greek.

3. **Spanish and Italian Borrowings:** Words borrowed from Spanish and Italian languages mainly cover the fields of culture and art. For example, words such as “**ballet**”, “**fiesta**” and “**piano**” have been borrowed from these languages.

4. **The Global Pressure of American English:** At the end of the 20th century, with the global hegemony of America and the development of modern information technologies, words such as “**internet**”, “**startup**”, “**blog**”, “**social media**” entered other languages. This also reflects the expansion of English as a global means of communication.

Borrowed words not only enrich the language, but also reflect intercultural relations, economic and social exchanges, and globalization processes. Words borrowed into a language are an indicator of the proximity of the speakers of that language to another culture, way of life, or system of thought. For example, words borrowed from the Indian language such as “**yoga**” and “**guru**” are an indication of interest in and influence on Indian culture.

Borrowed words also reflect cultural diversity and social change. In modern society, especially in the context of globalization, new borrowings appear in the English language every day. These words describe new technologies, modern social relations, and global issues.

There are several ways in which a borrowed word can adapt to the language it is passing through.

Transcription — this is the borrowing of a word unit, where its sound form is preserved, but sometimes it undergoes minor changes in accordance with the phonetic characteristics of the borrowed language that is borrowed. For example, some words borrowed from English: *football*, *trailer*, *jeans*, *sport*, *labour*, *travel*, *people*, *castle*, *fortress* and others. Examples of this are the words *regime*, *ballet*, *bouquet* and others that came to English from French. Such words represent a new sound complex in a foreign language, although each of their sound components (with rare exceptions) is replaced by sound units of the language that is borrowed.

Transliteration — this is a method of obtaining the spelling form of a foreign word: the letters of the borrowed word are replaced by the letters of the language from which it passes. During transliteration, the word is read according to the rules of reading in the native language. For example, words such as *cruise* (kruiz), *motel* (motel), *club* (klub) have been borrowed from English into Azerbaijani, as well as numerous proper nouns in English, such as *Washington* (Vaşinqton), *Texas* (Teksas), *London* (London) by this method. There are many words in English borrowed from ancient Greek, Latin and French and which retain their graphic features, although they are pronounced according to the rules of reading in English.

Calque — this is a method of obtaining an absolute translation of a foreign word or expression.

Calques are words obtained by the correct repetition of a foreign word or phrase, that is, by preserving its morphological structure and logic by means of the receiving language. During calque, the components of the borrowed word or expression are translated separately and combined according to the example of the foreign word or expression. For example, the German noun *Vaterland* was translated in parts to form the English calque *Fatherland*.

Semantic borrowing — this is the addition of a new meaning (often figurative) to an already existing word. For example, the words *pioneer* and *brigade* existed in English, and under the influence of the “Soviet” era, these words acquired the meanings of “member of a children’s communist organization” and “labor collective”. Semantic borrowing is especially easy to realize in close related languages.

Transcription, transliteration, calque and semantic borrowing should be distinguished from translation methods. Although they have the same mechanism, they differ in results.

In most cases, gradual changes have occurred as a result of the internal laws of language development, while more rapid changes, especially in the field of vocabulary, have occurred as a result of external influences. However, in both cases, these changes have covered all aspects (levels, layers, aspects) of the language structure, although they have affected these areas in different ways.

In order for a language to fulfill its main function completely, that of a means of communication, its vocabulary must respond in a timely manner to changes occurring in all areas of human activity [4].

The enrichment of the English lexicon has been carried out mainly by its own internal means (combinations of words, affixation and reinterpretation of words). However, borrowings from other languages, due to the peculiarities of the existence of Englishmen, have caused greater consequences than for other languages. Quantitative and qualitative changes in the lexicon of the English language are associated with the history of the English people.

Finding out ways in which new phenomena are expressed through language helps to reveal the cognitive mechanisms involved in assimilating the interaction of language with reality and facilitates the understanding of the complex interaction between real-life phenomena and the various methods of their verbalization. The emergence of new words and word combinations as a result of borrowing, as well as the acquisition of new meanings by old words, indicates that there are gaps in the cognitive base of the language that are not expressed by specific words or that need to be expressed more precisely and differently.

The English language has been in close contact with various cultures and languages throughout history and therefore has borrowed numerous words from other languages. The cognitive features of borrowings play an important role in the assimilating and use of language. Cognitive linguistics, as one of the interconnected branches of cognitive science, is divided into three main directions in modern linguistics: generative, functional and cognitive linguistics. Many authors,

when looking at modern linguistics, especially emphasize these three directions. Some researchers prefer to combine the last two directions; in such cases, functional and formal directions are discussed, here the latter is understood as generative linguistics [8, p. 135]. Many researchers agree that one of the main principles of cognitive linguistics is interdisciplinary. One of the characteristics of cognitive linguistics is the attempt to unify individual research programs. Scientists identify a number of key positions that are characteristic of cognitive research. One of these positions is the principle of cognitivism, according to this principle, it is important to rely on information about the mind and the brain obtained from other disciplines in the study and description of general rules [23]. Thus, interdisciplinary should be taken into account as a key factor in cognitive linguistics.

Borrowed words enter the semantic system of a new language by retaining their original meanings. However, these words sometimes undergo certain moral changes when adapting to the new language. For example, the English word “ballet”, borrowed from French, was previously used to mean “art of dance”, but over time it began to be used more specifically to mean “classical dance”. Such type of changes show how semantic transformations occur in relation to the worldview and culture of the language users.

Borrowings are forced to adapt to the phonological system of each language. Borrowed words sometimes keep their original phonetic features, and sometimes they change according to the phonetic rules of that language. For example, the word “boutique” borrowed from French undergoes certain changes in terms of pronunciation in English. These changes indicate how they entered the phonological system of the language and how the brain assimilates new phonetic forms.

Borrowings are not only phonological and semantic, but also syntactically adapted to the structure of the language. For example, expressions borrowed from another language are used in the sentence structure or word combinations of one language according to certain rules. The English expression “status quo” is an expression borrowed from Latin, but in English this expression is used according to certain syntactic structures.

Understanding the cognitive features of borrowings allows us to draw several important conclusions regarding language acquisition and use:

Borrowings indicate the functioning of the brain’s binary memory systems. That is, as people acquire multiple languages, the meaning of borrowings is interpreted according to both the context of the previous language and the context of the new language. By linking these binary memories and meanings, the brain accepts and uses the new language structure.

Borrowings also reflect intercultural relations and differences. Each element of language reflects the way of thinking and worldview of that culture. Borrowings show the interaction of different cultures and the adaptability of language. Thus, cognitive analysis of borrow-

ings reveals that language is not only a means of communication, but also a system that reflects human perception and notion of culture.

Borrowings play an important role in the development and change of language. Words entering the English language lead to the creation of new language structures and stimulate the development of the language. This process shows how the brain adapts to the semantic and syntactic structures of the language. Also, entering of borrowings into the structure of the language leads to a richer and more diverse language.

The main role in being verbalized of the concepts of foreign cultures into the language is played by the mass media, because the language of the mass media is currently one of the productive sources that increase vocabulary.

The main reason for receiving of a borrowed and foreign concept is the existence of conceptual gaps in the culture into which the word is entered. In this case, the need to name new facts of modern life is met.

V.I According to Karasik, such quasi-concepts, which express realities borrowed from other cultures, cannot be called concepts, because there are no valuable or ethno-cultural features here [2, p. 213].

The UK and US media use borrowings primarily in order to activate them as language reflection and language play.

A concept – this is something that exists both in consciousness and in language, which defines (names, represents in the form of an image) phenomena (notions, actions, cases) that are of primary importance in people’s lives and in their communication (including speech communication). This thing has both universal and nationally determined significance and continuity over time [3, p. 9].

For example, the expression **#MeToo** emerged in America as a product of national-cultural mentality, but spread throughout the world through social networks and is currently used as complex nouns, for example, in German, Russian, and other languages.

#MeToo refers to a social movement and slogan. The expression is used to share and fight against the experiences of women, especially those who have experienced sexual harassment or raping. **#MeToo** movement spread widely on social media in 2017, and many women began sharing their stories, drawing public attention to the prevalence of sexual harassment and sexual violence.

#MeToo movement aims to support women when they experience sexual harassment and violence, to prevent such incidents, and to ensure that society takes this issue more seriously. As a result of the spread of this movement, many celebrities, especially those in the film and television industry, have begun to speak openly about sexual harassment and other forms of violence.

The emergence of new concepts and new lexical units that verbalize them reflects changes in society. Since English is the language of international and global communication, new lexical units that emerge in English almost immediately appear in the mass media in different languages, especially in advertising texts.

Acting as a classifier of human experience, the word is a necessary tool for learning about the world. According to the American researcher H. Putnam, the meaning of the word is a vector that directs the attention of language users to reality and sends them to knowledge about the world [2].

The issue of expanding the vocabulary, enriching the semantic code of various languages, filling in the lacunas is one of the most urgent issues of scientific development in this period. This can be achieved by fulfilling such a complex task as “solving the initial ‘coding’ of the content side of the language sign” [6, p. 27].

Researchers note that the number of native words in the lexicon of modern English is about 30%. In English, there are borrowings from more than 50 languages (Latin, French, Italian, Spanish, Dutch, Russian, German, oriental languages, etc.) [8, p.22-26].

In this regard, the large number of borrowed words in English has given some linguists reason to argue that English has lost its uniqueness and is a “hybrid language”. However, it should not be forgotten that the English language has never left its own existence, because its grammatical structure has hardly been affected by foreign influences. Despite numerous borrowings from other languages, the English language has not lost its origin and has continued to remain a language of the Germanic language group with all its characteristic features throughout its development.

If we are talking about the cognitive features of borrowings in English, it is absolutely necessary to mention the concepts. English is a language that has been in contact with numerous cultures throughout its history, and these relations have played an important role in the development of the language and, in particular, in the enrichment of its lexical structure. The topic of concepts and borrowings in English is an important area that reflects the dynamic development of the language, the emergence of new meanings, and socio-cultural changes.

Concepts represent brain structures that are used by humans to understand reality. Concepts are found in the lexicon of a language not only in the theoretical or intellectual field, but also in terms that reflect the social life of culture and society. Concepts in English explain how experience and worldview emerge through language. This shows how language is adapted to create deep connections and meanings in different areas of human experience.

Borrowed words are words that one language borrows from another and adapts them to the phonetic, grammatical, and semantic rules of that language. The English language has thousands of borrowings due to its rich history and cultural exchanges. Borrowings in English have been borrowed from a variety of languages, especially Latin, French, Greek, German, Spanish, Italian, and in recent years, from China and the languages of other countries. These words not only enrich the vocabulary of the language, but also reflect the thought and social structures of the language.

Concepts in English are dynamic and complex structures that play a major role in the development of the language. The change of concepts takes place according to the social, economic and cultural changes of

worldview and society. This leads to the replacement of traditional ideas by new, more complex and modern notions in the development of the language. For example, the concept of “**success**” can express not only personal achievements, but also collective development and progress, depending on the cultural and social conditions of the time.

Concepts in English and the words they represent are not only contemporary, but also reflect notions acquired in ancient times. Words such as “**democracy**”, “**freedom**”, “**justice**” are important parts of both the language and the cultural identity of a society. These words may have different meanings in different periods, but they always convey the basic notions of social and political thought.

Conclusion

The cognitive features of borrowings in English allow us to better understand how language works and is perceived in our brains. Borrowings, in addition to causing changes in the semantic, phonological and syntactic systems of the language, are also closely related to cross-cultural relations and perceptual mechanisms of the brain. This phenomenon shows that language is not only a means of communication, but also a process that reflects how a person thinks and perceives the world. Cognitive analysis of borrowings is an important approach to follow language development and change, and will play a significant role in future linguistic research.

In conceptology, the word is considered as a sign that carries the concept with all its content forms that manifest itself in text and action. Based on this, we can argue that in the process of borrowing lexical units from another language, concepts of other cultures are acquired, which happens as a result of acquaintance with the culture of a foreign language and acceptance of foreign forms of national mentality through lexical units.

Concepts and borrowings in English are important aspects of the development of the language and the dynamic development of society. Based on the extensive borrowings and connections with numerous cultures, the English language keeps its cultural identity and represents social and economic relations in the modern world. Analysis of concepts and borrowings shows that language is more than just a means of communication, but also how people understand and interpret the world, and how they perceive social and cultural structures. Research in this field proves that language is not only a means of communication, but also an important echo of culture, history and social reality.

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